

Studies on the Effect of Ultra-violet Light on Colloids.

Part I.

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The effects of ultra-violet light and of radium and X-rays on colloidal solutions have been the subject of numerous investigations. In a previous paper (Ganguly and Dhar, *Kolloid Z.*, 1922, 31, 16) one of us has shown that tropical sunlight is equally effective in coagulating colloidal solutions. In the case of certain colloids like colloidal gold, coagulation is brought about only after long exposure to ultra-violet light, whereas in the case of a number of other colloids, notably the metallic sulphides, coagulation is easily brought about by exposure to ordinary sunlight. Coagulation of colloids by heat is also known. Thus practically all kinds of radiation are capable of changing the size of colloidal particles.

No definite explanation of the mechanism of coagulation by light is yet available. There are two possible directions in which an explanation might be sought. The phenomenon might be an entirely physical one, where coagulation by light is merely a neutralisation of the charge on the particles, or it might be an altogether different process, where coagulation is mainly due to slow chemical changes in the system.

The effect of ultra-violet light on any solution would be the generation of electrons. As a result of this the bulk of the solution would be, for the time being, a seat of an extra positive charge. Coagulation of a negatively charged colloidal solution by ultra-violet light, might reasonably be explained as being due to the neutralisation of the negative charge on the colloid particles by the free positive charge in the solution. If this explanation be accepted it must necessarily follow that ultra-violet light should have no coagulating influence on positively charged colloidal solutions and should in every case coagulate negatively charged sols. The available experimental data, however, do not support the above view. In his monograph "Das Radium und Die Farben", Doelter, as a result of numerous investigations on the action of radium and

ultra-violet rays, has shown that positively charged manganese, iron, chromium and aluminium hydroxide sols are visibly altered on exposure to ultra-violet light for a period of 2-6 hours. It has been found that a series of positively charged hydroxide sols like cerium, thorium and zirconium hydroxide sols are easily changed on exposure to ultra-violet light. Doelter also claims that a negatively charged sulphur sol was not coagulated by exposure to ultra-violet light, which, however, is doubtful in view of the observations of Raffo and Rossi (*Kolloid Z.*, 1912, 11, 123). Thus experimental observations show beyond doubt that ultra-violet light can coagulate both positively and negatively charged colloids, its action being in no way limited to negatively charged sols.

Investigations on the coagulating action of radium rays have failed to throw any definite light on the problem. If the neutralisation of the charge on the particle, lay at the basis of the coagulation of colloids by different radium rays, one would expect, in that case, the negatively charged β -rays to coagulate only positively charged colloids and to have no influence on negatively charged sols. As will be seen, however, from the accompanying table,* there is no definite relationship between the sign of the charge on the colloid particle and the sign of the charge of the radium rays, which bring about coagulation.

The effect of β -rays on the coagulation of colloids.

Nature of the colloid.	Charge on the colloid.	Source of β -rays.	Observations.	Author.
Alkaline blood globulin.	Negative.	RaBr ₂	Coagulation.	Hardy.
Acidified blood globulin.	Positive.	RaBr ₂	No coagulation	Hardy.
Ferric hydroxide.	Positive.	0.1 gm. RaBr ₂	No coagulation.	Henri & Meyer.
Silver sol.	Negative.	0.1 gm. RaBr ₂	No coagulation.	Henri & Meyer.
Manganese, iron chromium and aluminium hydroxide sols.	Positive.	0.5 gm. RaCl ₂	No coagulation.	Doelter.
Ferric hydroxide.	Positive.	—	Very slow coagulation.	Righi.
Silver sol.	Negative.	0.015 gm. RaBr ₂ .	No coagulation.	Jorissen and Woudstra.
Chromium hydroxide sol.	Positive.	0.015 gm. RaBr ₂ .	Less stable towards electrolytes.	Jorissen and Woudstra.

* A complete bibliography on this subject is given by Nordenson (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1915, 90, 603).

Studies on the effect of X-ray radiations on colloids afford some evidence in favour of the charge neutralisation theory. Crowther and his co-workers (*Phil. Mag.*, 1927, 4, 825; 1929, 7, 86) have come to the conclusion that under the influence of X-ray radiations, negatively charged sols remain unaffected, whereas positively charged sols are invariably coagulated. Galecki (*Kolloid Z.*, 1912, 10, 149), however, found an increase in the size of gold particles exposed to X-ray radiations, whereas Bhatnagar (*Indian Science Congress Abstracts*, 1929) in his recent experiments has failed to observe any coagulation with both positively and negatively charged copper sols. It is thus clear that in the absence of further experimental data, a definite conclusion on this point is difficult.

The chemical explanation of the coagulation of colloids by light is not without its supporters. Schaum (*Kolloid Z.*, 1914, 15, 103) is of opinion that the action of light on colloids is not a physical process, but depends on a chemical change of either the dispersion medium, or of foreign substances, like traces of electrolytes, present in the colloid system. Similar views have also been expressed by Stintzing (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1914, 6, 231).

In the following experiments an attempt has been made to experimentally test the chemical view-point with regard to the coagulation of colloids by light. A number of colloidal solutions have been exposed to ultra-violet light from a mercury vapour lamp. The hydrogen ion concentration of the clear supernatant liquid after the hydrosols have been coagulated by light, has been determined. This value has been compared with the hydrogen ion concentration of the clear liquid obtained by ultra-filtration or by high speed centrifugalisation of a fresh sample of the same hydrosol. For acid solutions, the quinhydrone electrode was used to measure hydrogen ion concentrations, alkaline solutions being measured with the hydrogen electrode. The following experimental results were obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Sulphide Sols.

Colloidal solutions of arsenic and cadmium sulphides were prepared by the usual methods and freed from hydrogen sulphide, as far as possible, by passing a current of hydrogen. Colloidal antimony sulphide was prepared from antimony potassium tartrate,

and after being treated with a current of hydrogen was further purified by dialysis. A colloidal solution of ferrous sulphide was prepared by passing a current of hydrogen sulphide through a dilute alkaline solution of ferrous sulphate, and was purified by dialysis. A part of each of these colloidal solutions was filtered through an ultra-filter, the filtration being repeated till a clear filtrate was obtained. Another part was exposed in a quartz tube to a mercury vapour lamp, the tubes being placed at a distance of 10 cm. from the lamp. The exposure was continued till the whole of the colloid was precipitated. The p_H values of the clear filtrates, before and after exposure, were determined and the following results obtained:—

Sol.	p_H (unexposed).	p_H (exposed).
Arsenic sulphide	4.70	3.31
Cadmium ..	4.71	3.45
Antimony ..	4.01	3.10
Ferrous ..	6.53	7.60

Metallic Sols.

A colloidal solution of platinum was prepared by Bredig's method, and a sol of silver was prepared by Kohlschutter's process. A purple of Cassius sol was prepared by the addition of 10 c.c. of a 0.3% solution of gold chloride and 12.5 c.c. of a 0.5% solution of stannous chloride containing a slight excess of hydrochloric acid, to 200 c.c. of water. The dark violet precipitate obtained on standing was washed free from chlorides and finally peptised by boiling with weakly ammoniated water. The clear purple sol obtained by the above method was purified by dialysis. All these solutions were treated like the sulphides and the following values obtained:—

Sol.	p_H (unexposed).	p_H (exposed).
Platinum ..	5.85	5.68
Kohlschutter's silver	—	No coagulation.
Purple of Cassius	6.35	6.63

Sulphur Sols.

A colloidal solution of sulphur was prepared by adding a saturated solution of sulphur in alcohol to a large volume of water. Another sol of sulphur was prepared by slowly adding 50 c.c.

concentrated sulphuric acid to an equal volume of a 3*N*-sodium thiosulphate and purified by dialysis till the external water was free from sulphates. Both sols were coagulated on exposure and gave the following p_H values:—

Sol.	p_H (unexposed).	p_H (exposed).
Odén's sulphur ...	6.42	2.24
Sulphur (by displacement of solvent).	6.43	6.17

Hydroxide Sols.

Colloidal solutions of cerium and thorium hydroxides were prepared by the dialysis of 10% solutions of ceric ammonium nitrate and of thorium nitrate respectively. A ferric hydroxide sol was prepared by the addition of a solution of ferric chloride to a large volume of boiling water, and purified by dialysis. After a day's exposure the sols were filtered and the p_H values of the filtrates measured:—

Sol.	p_H (unexposed).	p_H (exposed).
Cerium hydroxide ...	6.41	6.73
Thorium ..	5.91	6.68
Ferric ..	—	No coagulation.

Prussian Blue Sols.

The sol was prepared by the dialysis of a solution of Prussian blue in oxalic acid. The following p_H values were obtained:—

Sol.	p_H (unexposed).	p_H (exposed).
Prussian blue	6.96	6.11

Gum Mastic Sol.

The gum mastic sol was prepared by pouring an alcoholic solution of the gum in a large volume of water. The following p_H values were obtained:—

Sol.	p_H (unexposed).	p_H (exposed).
Gum mastic	6.31	6.04

Discussion of Results.

During the coagulation by light of arsenic, antimony and cadmium sulphide sols the following changes are observed : The sol first becomes turbid but retains its original colour, part of the sol is then precipitated, the colour becoming whitish. On further exposure practically the whole of the sulphide is precipitated, but the supernatant liquid is still a pale yellowish-white suspension. Finally all the solution is completely precipitated leaving a clear liquid. All these observations can be satisfactorily explained on the basis of chemical reactions brought about by exposure to ultra-violet light.

As is well-known, the sulphide sols owe their stability to the presence of hydrogen sulphide in the system, part of which is adsorbed on the surface of the colloid particles. Hydrogen sulphide in presence of water is easily oxidised on exposure to ultra-violet light generating sulphur acids. Two causes now contribute towards a diminution of the stability of the colloid: the coagulating action of the small amount of acid generated in the system, and the removal of a part of the stabilising ion by oxidation (Freundlich and Nathansohn, *Kolloid Z.*, 1921, 28, 258). A part of the colloid is thus precipitated. A secondary reaction between the hydrogen sulphide and its products of oxidation produces sulphur in small concentrations which remains suspended as a sol. As the exposure is continued more of the sulphide is precipitated, generating a further amount of sulphur which forms a suspension in the beginning but finally gets precipitated when its concentration becomes sufficiently large. An analysis of the coagulum showed that it contained a quantity of sulphur which could be extracted easily by treatment with a suitable solvent. The supernatant liquid after total precipitation of the sol is fairly acidic as is shown by its p_H value.

Unlike arsenic sulphide, ferrous sulphide sol on exposure to light shows an increase in the p_H value of the filtrate after coagulation. Here, as in the case of other metal sulphides, stabilisation of the colloid is due to hydrogen sulphide. The primary action of light is to oxidise the hydrogen sulphide. This destruction of the stabilising electrolyte brings about the coagulation of the colloid. A secondary action now sets in between the iron sulphide and the sulphur oxide produced by the oxidation of hydrogen sulphide, whereby the latter products are all used up. The iron sulphide is converted into complex basic salts and precipitated as such (Berthelot and Gaudechon,

Compt. rend., 1911, 152, 376). Ferrous sulphide does not develop an increased acidity like arsenic sulphide because of the above secondary reaction.

Bredig's platinum sol on exposure develops a slightly increased acidity. The nature of the particles in a Bredig sol is not clearly understood. The action of ultra-violet rays is probably the completion of the hydrolysis of the particles, which would account for the slightly increased acidity (*cf.* Eastlack, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 37, 2667).

The sulphur sol prepared from sodium thiosulphate showed the most remarkable change in the p_H value after its coagulation by light. The acidity of the final filtrate was found to be due to sulphuric acid, which must have been generated, partly by the decomposition of the pentathionic acid adsorbed on the surface of the colloid particles, and, partly by the oxidation of the sulphur particles themselves. A very marked increase in the conductivity was observed by Raffo and Rossi (*loc. cit.*), when a similarly prepared sulphur sol was coagulated by light. The pronounced change in the p_H values, and in the conductivity as observed by Raffo and Rossi, establish beyond doubt that a series of chemical changes are brought about in the colloid system when it is exposed to light. It is not intended, however, in the present experiment, to follow the nature of these changes.

Colloidal solutions of cerium and thorium hydroxides when exposed to ultra-violet light show a decrease in the hydrogen ion concentration after exposure. A possible explanation for this decrease in acidity, on the basis of chemical reactions brought about by light may be as follows: Under the circumstances in which these hydroxide sols are prepared, they retain a small quantity of nitric acid which is not easily removed by dialysis. The sol sets to a jelly if the dialysis be carried too far, as has been shown by Fernau and Pauli (*Kolloid Z.*, 1917, 20, 20) and also by Kruyt (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1923, (iv), 42, 1923). In all probability, a part of the acid is adsorbed on the surface of the colloid particles, and a part remains in solution in the dispersion medium, there being a certain equilibrium between the amount adsorbed and the amount in solution in the water. The primary action of ultra-violet light is to decompose a part of the acid present in the dispersion medium.* This disturbs

* The decomposition of concentrated nitric acid by light is well-known. Under the catalytic influence of the colloidal matter present in this system, even dilute

the equilibrium as a result of which a portion of the acid adsorbed on the surface of the colloid particles is given up to the aqueous medium, the colloid being rendered less stable than before. This process continues till the colloid begins to set. The reduced acidity is due to the partial decomposition of the nitric acid, which is the stabilising substance in the case of these colloids.

Prussian blue did not show any coagulation on exposure to ultra-violet light. The slight decrease in hydrogen ion concentration, after exposure, is probably due to the decomposition of the oxalic acid used to peptise the sol.

A gum mastic sol on exposure to ultra-violet light does not show any coagulation, but the filtrate after exposure shows a slight increase in the concentration of hydrogen ions. This effect is due to the same cause as produces a similar effect in the case of sulphur sol prepared by pouring a solution of sulphur in alcohol to a large volume of water. In both these cases the difference in the p_H values is due to the oxidation of the alcohol present in the system, the colloidal particles acting as catalysts for the above process.

In the case of practically all the colloids studied the p_H value of the filtrate of the unexposed sol has been found more or less different from the p_H value of the solution left after coagulation of the colloid by ultra-violet light. Most of the colloidal solutions studied have been purified, as far as possible, by dialysis and other methods. Consequently the electrolytes present in the colloid systems are mostly those which are either themselves adsorbed on the surface of the colloid particles or are subsequently generated by chemical actions on adsorbed ions and electrolytes. Since considerable differences in the p_H values have actually been obtained, it has to be admitted that chemical action does take place on exposure of colloids to light, mainly at the expense of adsorbed ions and electrolytes. In addition to the adsorbed electrolyte, the dispersed substance itself might undergo a change in its chemical nature. Although this does happen in a few cases, *e.g.*, in the case of ferrous sulphide, the behaviour is by no means a general one.

The sols studied during the present experiments were all hydrosols. On exposure to ultra-violet light, a chemical change in the dispersion medium, except for the formation of minute quantities of

nitric acid may reasonably be expected to be photochemically active (*cf.* Moore and Webster, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1913, 87 [B], 163).

hydrogen peroxide, is not likely. This hydrogen peroxide, generated by the action of ultra-violet light on water, is probably not capable of bringing about a direct oxidation. When added to cerium hydroxide sol, hydrogen peroxide produced no direct change (Fernau and Pauli, *loc. cit.*), whereas in the case of a gold sol, hydrogen peroxide brings about a reduction of any oxidised particles to metallic gold (Nordensohn, *loc. cit.*).

It should be stated that the p_H values of the filtrates, as obtained in these experiments, are not absolute measures of the total hydrogenion contents of the system. In the total absence of chemical action, however, effects due to adsorption by the flocculated mass of precipitates should be the same in the case of coagulation by ultra-filtration as in the case of coagulation by light. Consequently except in the case of very fine colloids containing a large proportion of amicros, observed differences in the p_H values will give a true indication as to whether a chemical action has taken place or not.

The stability and the charge of a colloidal solution are due to adsorbed ions. When a colloid is exposed to ultra-violet light, a chemical change sets in, which brings about a corresponding change in the hydrogen ion concentration of the colloid system. The chemical changes are at the expense of the ions or electrolytes adsorbed on the surface of the colloid particles. This results in the destruction of the stabilising influence of the adsorbed substances, and in the coagulation of the colloid. This fact lies at the basis of the coagulation of colloids by light. The above conclusion is supported by the recent experiments of Miss Roy and Dhar (*Indian Science Congress Abstracts*, 1929).

Further work is in progress.

Summary.

1. A number of colloidal solutions have been exposed to ultra-violet light and the p_H values of the clear filtrates, obtained before and after exposure, have been measured.
2. It has been found that both positively and negatively charged colloids are coagulated by ultra-violet light. These observations can not be satisfactorily explained on the basis of the physical theory of coagulation.

3. Distinct and well marked changes in the p_{H} values on exposure to ultra-violet light have been observed. Attempts have been made to interpret these in the light of known chemical and photo-chemical reactions.

4. The coagulation of colloids by ultra-violet light is due mainly to the destruction of the stabilising agents as a result of the chemical changes brought about by light.

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